

A Statistical Analysis of Algorithm Performance

Tables 1 to 12 present the results of statistical hypothesis testing, comparing the proposed method against CatCMA and ICatCMA in terms of success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts, across all benchmark problems and settings reported in Section 4.4. Note that to accurately compare total computational cost, the statistics related to the number of total FEs and restarts reported in this section include all runs rather than only the successful ones, in contrast to Figures 1 and 2 of the main paper. These data demonstrate the statistical significance of the following general trends discussed in Section 4.4:

1. In both the $d_c = d_x = 5$ and $d_c = d_x = 10$ cases, for weak interaction regimes (small a), CatCMA outperforms IGBD.
2. Otherwise, IGBD largely outperforms both CatCMA and ICatCMA.
3. In the $d_c = d_x = 5$ case, CatCMA is able to solve type-IV interaction using hundreds of restarts, suggesting a random search-like behavior.

Table 1. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{II} with $d_c = d_x = 5$ as a function of a . The main quantity and the parenthesized quantity represent the median and the IQR, respectively. The symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$ indicate that a quantity is statistically significantly higher or lower than the corresponding quantity for the proposed method under a Wilcoxon rank-sum test ($p < 0.05$) with a Bonferroni correction accounting for all comparisons performed across Tables 1 to 12; the absence of a symbol indicates no statistically significant difference.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	5.26E+3 (1.14E+3)	6.95E+2 (7.75E+1) $\downarrow$	1.69E+4 (1.40E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
1	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	9.51E+3 (5.28E+3)	7.20E+2 (1.10E+2) $\downarrow$	1.69E+4 (1.26E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
2	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	9.66E+3 (4.08E+3)	2.44E+4 (4.53E+4)	1.74E+4 (1.39E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	19 (36) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
4	Success rate	1.00	0.05 $\downarrow$	1.00
	Total FEs	8.94E+3 (3.28E+3)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	1.86E+4 (8.54E+2) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	392 (2) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
8	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
	Total FEs	9.68E+3 (3.96E+3)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	1.97E+4 (1.60E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	404 (2) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
16	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
	Total FEs	1.01E+4 (2.03E+3)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.09E+4 (2.00E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	386 (3) $\uparrow$	0 (0)

Table 2. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{II+IV} with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^2$ and $d_c = d_x = 5$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	6.54E+3 (7.52E+2)	1.18E+3 (2.90E+2) $\downarrow$	2.15E+4 (1.96E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
1	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	1.03E+4 (3.84E+3)	2.79E+3 (2.87E+3) $\downarrow$	2.21E+4 (1.17E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	1 (2)	0 (0)
2	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	1.04E+4 (3.43E+3)	1.75E+4 (3.64E+4)	2.45E+4 (2.30E+4) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	9 (22) $\uparrow$	0 (1)
4	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
	Total FEs	9.75E+3 (5.74E+3)	3.77E+4 (7.91E+4) $\uparrow$	6.19E+4 (8.62E+4) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	23 (50) $\uparrow$	2 (3)
8	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.85
	Total FEs	1.05E+4 (3.54E+3)	5.00E+4 (5.07E+4) $\uparrow$	2.66E+5 (3.01E+5) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	30 (31) $\uparrow$	10 (12) $\uparrow$
16	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.25 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.22E+4 (5.33E+3)	3.89E+4 (3.61E+4) $\uparrow$	5.00E+5 (6.71E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	22 (22) $\uparrow$	18 (0) $\uparrow$

Table 3. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem $f_{\text{II+IV}}$ with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^6$ and $d_c = d_x = 5$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.05 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	2.66E+4 (4.61E+4)	3.59E+3 (3.70E+2) $\downarrow$	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	12 (0) $\uparrow$
1	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.15 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	2.63E+4 (3.07E+4)	3.23E+4 (3.46E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	10 (11) $\uparrow$	12 (0) $\uparrow$
2	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.10 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	4.45E+4 (2.39E+4)	1.82E+4 (1.84E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	5 (6) $\uparrow$	12 (1) $\uparrow$
4	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.05 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	4.13E+4 (2.01E+4)	7.03E+4 (5.74E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	22 (19) $\uparrow$	11 (1) $\uparrow$
8	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.10 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	3.64E+4 (2.00E+4)	3.48E+4 (4.54E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	10 (14) $\uparrow$	11 (0) $\uparrow$
16	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.05 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	4.92E+4 (3.57E+4)	7.73E+4 (1.32E+5)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	24 (41) $\uparrow$	11 (0) $\uparrow$

Table 4. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{III} with $d_c = d_x = 5$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
0	Total FEs	1.01E+4 (4.99E+3)	2.02E+3 (3.19E+3) $\downarrow$	1.99E+4 (2.11E+4) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	1 (3)	0 (1)
	Success rate	1.00	0.20 $\downarrow$	1.00
1	Total FEs	1.36E+4 (3.28E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.01E+4 (2.46E+4)
	Restarts	0 (0)	404 (6) $\uparrow$	0 (1)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.95
2	Total FEs	3.51E+4 (5.11E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	1.72E+5 (2.32E+5)
	Restarts	0 (0)	394 (6) $\uparrow$	6 (10) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.95
4	Total FEs	1.93E+4 (1.62E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	1.02E+5 (8.93E+4) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	412 (6) $\uparrow$	3 (3) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.75
8	Total FEs	1.79E+4 (1.58E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.86E+5 (3.16E+5) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	538 (15) $\uparrow$	13 (14) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	0.95	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.75
16	Total FEs	2.02E+4 (2.90E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.99E+5 (2.82E+5) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	662 (21) $\uparrow$	14 (14) $\uparrow$

Table 5. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem $f_{\text{III+IV}}$ with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^2$ and $d_c = d_x = 5$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.05 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.26E+4 (9.44E+3)	2.33E+4 (2.32E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	15 (15) $\uparrow$	15 (0) $\uparrow$
1	Success rate	0.95	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.19E+4 (1.15E+4)	1.94E+4 (2.15E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	13 (14) $\uparrow$	15 (0) $\uparrow$
2	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.83E+4 (3.30E+4)	4.19E+4 (1.08E+5)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	28 (70) $\uparrow$	15 (0) $\uparrow$
4	Success rate	1.00	0.90	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.11E+4 (4.54E+3)	8.83E+4 (1.66E+5) $\uparrow$	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	64 (119) $\uparrow$	15 (1) $\uparrow$
8	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.32E+4 (8.24E+3)	4.51E+4 (9.72E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	31 (68) $\uparrow$	15 (1) $\uparrow$
16	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.53E+4 (1.32E+4)	1.81E+4 (2.72E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	15 (24) $\uparrow$	31 (1) $\uparrow$

Table 6. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem $f_{\text{III+IV}}$ with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^6$ and $d_c = d_x = 5$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
0	Total FEs	1.71E+4 (7.50E+3)	6.78E+4 (7.45E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	30 (33) $\uparrow$	11 (1) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
1	Total FEs	1.96E+4 (1.52E+4)	3.26E+4 (5.11E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	13 (20) $\uparrow$	11 (0) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
2	Total FEs	2.54E+4 (2.94E+4)	9.36E+3 (2.07E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	3 (9) $\uparrow$	11 (0) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
4	Total FEs	1.86E+4 (8.11E+3)	5.88E+4 (6.29E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	28 (31) $\uparrow$	10 (1) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
8	Total FEs	1.84E+4 (5.05E+3)	2.68E+4 (3.86E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	10 (18) $\uparrow$	10 (1) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$
16	Total FEs	1.97E+4 (6.37E+3)	5.98E+4 (4.73E+4)	5.00E+5 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	27 (22) $\uparrow$	10 (2) $\uparrow$

Table 7. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{II} with $d_c = d_x = 10$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
0	Total FEs	1.20E+4 (2.12E+3)	1.34E+3 (1.68E+2) $\downarrow$	7.41E+4 (8.80E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
1	Total FEs	2.53E+4 (1.13E+4)	1.44E+3 (1.47E+2) $\downarrow$	7.05E+4 (4.95E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
2	Total FEs	2.67E+4 (6.01E+3)	1.59E+3 (2.25E+2) $\downarrow$	7.20E+4 (5.71E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
4	Total FEs	2.80E+4 (9.39E+3)	7.79E+4 (2.06E+5)	8.12E+4 (5.72E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	32 (88) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
8	Total FEs	2.78E+4 (1.31E+4)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	8.45E+4 (5.53E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	927 (4) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
16	Total FEs	2.97E+4 (8.73E+3)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	8.88E+4 (9.94E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	926 (5) $\uparrow$	0 (0)

Table 8. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{II+IV} with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^2$ and $d_c = d_x = 10$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
0	Total FEs	1.72E+4 (3.17E+3)	3.02E+3 (3.21E+2) $\downarrow$	9.16E+4 (9.93E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
1	Total FEs	3.54E+4 (9.76E+3)	5.03E+4 (1.03E+5)	9.36E+4 (5.17E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	11 (26) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
2	Total FEs	3.38E+4 (8.54E+3)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	1.04E+5 (4.86E+3) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	606 (6) $\uparrow$	0 (0)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
4	Total FEs	3.98E+4 (1.37E+4)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.70E+5 (7.03E+5) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	641 (2) $\uparrow$	2 (6)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.20
8	Total FEs	6.98E+4 (7.67E+4)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	618 (1) $\uparrow$	17 (0) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
16	Total FEs	3.15E+5 (3.97E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	606 (3) $\uparrow$	16 (0) $\uparrow$

Table 9. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{II+IV} with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^6$ and $d_c = d_x = 10$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	0.15	1.00 $\uparrow$	0.00
	Total FEs	2.00E+6 (3.47E+3)	2.37E+4 (2.25E+4) $\downarrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	2 (1)	1 (2)	8 (1) $\uparrow$
1	Success rate	0.65	0.00	0.00
	Total FEs	1.77E+6 (1.23E+6)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	0 (2)	251 (1) $\uparrow$	7 (1) $\uparrow$
2	Success rate	0.80	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00
	Total FEs	1.13E+6 (9.73E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	0 (1)	249 (2) $\uparrow$	7 (0) $\uparrow$
4	Success rate	0.85	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00
	Total FEs	9.06E+5 (7.81E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	0 (0)	245 (2) $\uparrow$	7 (0) $\uparrow$
8	Success rate	0.80	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00
	Total FEs	8.74E+5 (9.77E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	0 (0)	240 (1) $\uparrow$	7 (0) $\uparrow$
16	Success rate	0.60	0.00	0.00
	Total FEs	1.30E+6 (1.02E+6)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	0 (0)	235 (1) $\uparrow$	7 (0) $\uparrow$

Table 10. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem f_{III} with $d_c = d_x = 10$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
	Success rate	1.00	1.00	1.00
0	Total FEs	3.42E+4 (2.00E+4)	1.89E+4 (4.55E+4)	3.61E+5 (4.08E+5) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	8 (22) $\uparrow$	4 (5)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
1	Total FEs	7.22E+4 (1.11E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.48E+5 (2.37E+5)
	Restarts	0 (1)	906 (8) $\uparrow$	2 (2)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
2	Total FEs	7.87E+4 (9.68E+4)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	3.48E+5 (4.76E+5)
	Restarts	0 (0)	939 (10) $\uparrow$	3 (6)
	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	1.00
4	Total FEs	1.19E+5 (2.16E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.75E+5 (3.85E+5)
	Restarts	0 (0)	1915 (56) $\uparrow$	2 (4)
	Success rate	0.85	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.70
8	Total FEs	2.70E+5 (8.85E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	1.13E+6 (1.36E+6)
	Restarts	0 (1)	2006 (70) $\uparrow$	10 (14) $\uparrow$
	Success rate	0.95	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.80
16	Total FEs	2.59E+5 (5.52E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	1.03E+6 (1.12E+6)
	Restarts	0 (1)	2338 (37) $\uparrow$	8 (10)

Table 11. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem $f_{\text{III+IV}}$ with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^2$ and $d_c = d_x = 10$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	1.00	0.05 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	7.04E+4 (7.02E+4)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	778 (6) $\uparrow$	14 (1) $\uparrow$
1	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	1.42E+5 (1.65E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	792 (8) $\uparrow$	14 (1) $\uparrow$
2	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	5.85E+4 (1.12E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	772 (4) $\uparrow$	13 (1) $\uparrow$
4	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	9.35E+4 (6.93E+4)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	738 (6) $\uparrow$	11 (0) $\uparrow$
8	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	2.02E+5 (2.13E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	674 (9) $\uparrow$	12 (2) $\uparrow$
16	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.10 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	3.77E+5 (7.73E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (1)	1284 (28) $\uparrow$	16 (2) $\uparrow$

Table 12. Comparison of the success rate, total number of function evaluations (FEs), and number of restarts of ICatCMA and CatCMA against the proposed method on the benchmark problem $f_{\text{III+IV}}$ with $\kappa(\mathbf{A}) = 10^6$ and $d_c = d_x = 10$ as a function of a . The notation conventions for the median and IQR, as well as the statistical methodology and the meaning of the significance symbols $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$, follow Table 1.

a		IGBD (ours)	CatCMA	ICatCMA
0	Success rate	0.95	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	8.15E+5 (9.35E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (1)	454 (6) $\uparrow$	8 (0) $\uparrow$
1	Success rate	0.85	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00
	Total FEs	6.25E+5 (5.93E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0)
	Restarts	0 (0)	461 (5) $\uparrow$	8 (0) $\uparrow$
2	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	4.17E+5 (4.87E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	468 (2) $\uparrow$	8 (1) $\uparrow$
4	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	5.27E+5 (3.44E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (1)	470 (4) $\uparrow$	6 (1) $\uparrow$
8	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	4.52E+5 (5.29E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (0)	436 (7) $\uparrow$	6 (1) $\uparrow$
16	Success rate	1.00	0.00 $\downarrow$	0.00 $\downarrow$
	Total FEs	6.07E+5 (6.41E+5)	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$	2.00E+6 (0.00E+0) $\uparrow$
	Restarts	0 (1)	523 (10) $\uparrow$	9 (4) $\uparrow$